

Some New 6:8 Di-iodo-S-Substituted-2-thio-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-4(3H)-Quinazolones

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The therapeutic effect of 4(3H)quinazolone derivatives has been demonstrated in case of simian and avian malarial infections^{1,2}. A number of 2- and 4-sulphanilamidoquinazolines³ has been reported to be antimalarials exhibiting Schizonticidal activity. Dhatt and Bami⁴ synthesised 2-ethyl-6-methyl-3-*o*-methoxyphenyl-4(3H)quinazolone which exhibits some activity against *P. gallinaceum* in chicks. Also, febrifugine, an alkaloid having 3-substituted 4-quinazolone structure, have been reported to possess high antimalarial activity though of a low therapeutic index⁵.

In view of the above observations, the authors synthesised some 6,8-di-iodo-2-S-substituted thio-3-aryl (or alkyl) 4(3H)quinazolones⁷ as possible antimalarials and ataractic agents⁸. In the present work, the synthesis is carried on by condensing aryl or alkyl-isothiocyanates with 3,5-di-iodoanthranilic acid⁹.

Pharmacological screening of these compounds is in progress and will be reported at a future date.

EXPERIMENTAL

6 : 8-Di-iodo-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)quinazolone : A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (6 ml), 3 : 5-di-iodoanthranilic acid (20 gm) and absolute ethanol (70 ml) was refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was washed with ethanol, dissolved in 10% NaOH, precipitated with HCl, washed several times with water, and dried. It was crystallised from ethanol.

Similarly various 6 : 8, di-iodo-2-mercapto-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolones were prepared from the corresponding aryl (or alkyl) isothiocyanates and 3 : 5 di-iodoanthranilic acid. (See Table 1).

6 : 8-Di-iodo-2-*n*-amylthio-3-phenyl-4(3H)quinazolones : To a solution of NaOH (5 gm) in 85 ml of 50% EtOH-H₂O, 6 : 8-di-iodo-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone (7.50 gm) was added. The solution was stirred, filtered and treated with *n*-amyl iodide (5 ml). After being stirred for another hour, the crystalline product was washed (H₂O, EtOH). Long needles were obtained on crystallisation from ethanol.

Similarly, various 6 : 8, di-iodo-S-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4(3H)-quinazolones have been prepared (See Tables 2-4).

TABLE 1

6 : 8, *Di-iodo-2-mercapto-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4(3H)-quinazolones*

S.No.	Aryl (or alkyl group) -R-	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %		Sulphur, %	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl-	197	C ₁₄ H ₉ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.42	5.53	6.41	6.32
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl-	208	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.31	5.39	6.18	6.15
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl-	204	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.41	5.39	6.12	6.15
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-	200	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.36	5.39	6.21	6.15
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-	195	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ SN ₂ I ₂	5.19	5.22	5.92	5.99
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-	201	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ SN ₂ I ₂	5.01	5.09	5.94	5.82
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	165	C ₁₄ H ₇ OSN ₂ ClI ₂	5.21	5.18	5.91	5.92
8.	Benzyl-	180	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.35	5.39	6.16	6.15
9.	Butyl-	220	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ OSN ₂ I ₂	5.71	5.76	6.61	6.59

TABLE 2

6 : 8, *Di-iodo-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-2-isoamyl-thio-4(3H)-quinazolones*

S.No.	Aryl (or alkyl group) -R-	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %		Sulphur, %	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl-	92	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ SON ₂ I ₂	4.81	4.86	5.61	5.56
2.	-Tolyl-	144	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.72	4.75	5.44	5.42
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl-	82	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.64	4.75	5.46	5.42
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-	210	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SO ₂ N ₂ I ₂	4.71	4.62	5.21	5.28
5.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-	105	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ SO ₂ N ₂ I ₂	4.49	4.52	5.24	5.16
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	230	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ SOClN ₂ I ₂	4.61	4.59	5.14	5.24
7.	Butyl-	84	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ SON ₂ I ₂	5.12	5.94	5.77	5.75

TABLE 3

6 : 8, *Di-iodo-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-2n-amylthio-4(3H)-quinazolones*

S.No.	Aryl (or Alkyl group) -R-	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %		Sulphur, %	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl-	230	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ SON ₂ I ₂	4.76	4.86	5.61	5.56
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl-	204	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.73	4.75	5.47	5.42
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl-	194	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.81	4.75	5.44	5.42
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.69	4.75	5.41	5.42
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-	206	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SO ₂ N ₂ I ₂	4.66	4.62	5.30	5.28
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-	220	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ SO ₂ N ₂ I ₂	4.51	4.52	5.18	5.16
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	224	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ SOCIN ₂ I ₂	4.52	4.59	5.22	5.24
8.	Butyl-	298	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ SON ₂ I ₂	5.12	5.04	5.79	5.75
9.	Benzyl-	192	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ SON ₂ I ₂	4.71	4.75	5.48	5.42

TABLE 4

6 : 8, *Di-iodo-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-2-o-Nitrobenzylthio-4(3H)-quinazolones*

S.No.	Alkyl (or Aryl group) -R-	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %		Sulphur, %	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl-	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ SO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.51	6.55	4.51	4.99
2.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl-	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ SO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.42	6.41	4.91	4.89
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-	126	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ SO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.39	6.41	4.79	4.89
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-	136	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ SO ₄ N ₃ I ₂	6.25	6.26	4.81	4.77
5.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-	130	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ SO ₄ N ₃ I ₂	6.20	6.13	4.65	4.67
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-	128	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ SClO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.19	6.22	4.79	4.74
7.	Butyl-	129	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ SO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.74	6.76	5.25	5.15
8.	Benzyl-	114	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ SO ₃ N ₃ I ₂	6.43	6.41	4.91	4.89

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